

The hypothesis of the virtual reality world; according to astrophysical and mathematical presumption

I. Overviewing the creator's mind

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1

start September 15, 2015; finished June 16, 2017

ABSTRACT

Context. This paper suggests a hypothesis that the world is a simulation of a digital world done by a creator who is the ruler of the highest civilization. As this creator can control the cosmic distances and so he used his science and arts in a simulation called life, this life is based upon the creator strategies and those strategies are simple as your computer, you turn on your computer so the life began, but in the highest civilization computer there is no shut down, but a timer set according to the highest civilization order. It's because we are controlled by a higher civilization that we cannot go beyond them because they are at a higher dimension than ours, and mostly they are at the highest dimension that can get over all the dimensions of the hyperspace. Science is a dynamic process of questioning, hypothesizing, discovering, and changing previous ideas based on what is learned. Scientific ideas are developed through reasoning and tested against observations. Scientists assess and question each other's work in a critical process called peer review. Our understanding about the universe and our place in it has changed over time. New information can cause us to rethink what we know and reevaluate how we classify objects in order to better understand them. New ideas and perspectives can come from questioning a theory or seeing where a classification breaks down

Aims. The aim of this paper is to over viewing the data that the creator used to shape the hyperspace and ruling the life we live in and this incredible data is connected to achieve the main goal of life.

Methods. Collecting data and analyzing then connecting them

Results. A creator from a higher civilization made this hyperspace of multi-verse by using a special kind of programming

Key words. Origins of the universe – The philosophy of God

1. Introduction

As far back as recorded history goes, there have been two sets of opposing ideas, beliefs, theories, or teachings about the origin of the universe. It has either existed eternally with no beginning or end, or it was created at some point in time and will eventually come to an end. In the first part we examined earlier cultural, religious, and somewhat philosophical views of how the universe began. We've also spent a little time looking at some ideas about our own beginnings from a religious and scientific point of view. In this paper, we're going to take a brief excursion through the various theories that science has put forth to explain the origin of the universe.

The origin of the universe is related to the shape of the universe and to the structures of the universe as well, so everything in this world is connected because it's just like a scenario for a game having an end and a beginning, imagine the creator was totally alone and he told himself that he will design a game of good and evil, of heavens and hell and he began to do so, he began to plan for the beginning of the game, but firstly he must know what this game must be like and what it's contents, so the origin of the universe began according to the highest civilization decision that was like "begin" so it began, it's like turning on your computer, related to the computer we are the higher civilization that created it, according to the cartoon character we draw and program, we are the higher civilization, we can create and control them, so we are higher than them.

2. Conclusions

This paper is discussing and analyzing the origin of the universe, beginnings of life and how the creator is dealing with ruling and shaping the universe and still the connection between Philosophy and Astro-ph the best explanation we have for the origin of the universe. However, there are still gaps and inconsistencies in our knowledge, and perhaps the nagging suspicion that the more we learn and the more questions we answer, the more there is to learn and the more new questions arise.

3. The virtual reality world hypothesis

3.1. Overview of the presumption

According to a philosophy concept; We are living in a simulation created by a higher civilization, this higher civilization may compose of many creators or just one creator, but how does this simulation work. this question is meaning all the hyperspace we live in, so to understand how the hyperspace works we must understand the meaning of being in a bubble of a simulation, imagine that you are a coder, a coder means that you are someone who can create something by using codes, you write this codes in a special languages called programming languages like phython, C+, C sharp, Java and etc this languages you write it scripted or compiled to the system you are working on for example the

computer, then the computer turn it into codes which are 0 to 1, the computer system just knows those two 0 which means off or 1 which means on, these codes got into matrix, so they give you the something you wanted to build, but it's using specific kind of programming languages and it's more scripted than compiled, but still we don't know how the creator designed this bubble of hyperspace.

The creator scripted what he wants to do like life will goes like .. then event happens .. then etc etc etc etc he up-load this data into the server of his specific computer to read this code and then this code is read and turned it into one or zero and for sure it was one so the program is on, but this program won't start except the creator put a scripted line of a beginning and an end to this program, so the beginning was just an inflation of the information to the creator, but for us in the virtual world for the creator and the virtual reality world for us it looks like we feel it like an explosion and to be more accurate it's not an explosion, it's an inflation of energy, so what the creator did is that he wrote the scripted data and up-load it into the server then the server read it and turned it into actions, so the creator for example scripted the information will spread in a kind of an inflation, but to be accurate this information was not all the information, but it's the fuel or the spark that will led to the birth of other types of energy for us and information for the higher civilization, so everything is related to others because the start point was the fuel for all the other points.

We do live in a hyperspace of hyper dimensions, like we are in a bulk of cosmic sea, the inflated energy went every where making universes and those universes worked like budding universe producing many other universes in the bulk of hyper space, but this bulk of hyperspace is composed of levels or surfaces which depend on your dimension.

Imagine the hyperspace is like a bubble which contain other bubbles and those other bubbles contains bubbles and etc till the formation of 7 bubble inside the main bubble of hyperspace.

The data that was scripted was divided into sub-data which are:

- The origin and shape of the universe/multi-verse and life
- The origin of creatures and civilization
- The origin of curse and diseases
- The end scenario for the universe/multi-verse

3.1.1. The origin and shape of the universe/multi-verse and life

The origin of the universe, there are theories about the origin of the universe, but the most known one is the big bang, which states that there are a giant amount of energy inflated into the nothing to make it something, this stretch of the energy wasn't in just one direction, it was at all directions of the nothing that led it to be space or something.(14)

The inflated energy or information float in the cosmic sea of the hyperspace making universes like small bubbles in a deep sea, those bubble universes produced other bubble universes by using something like budding making multi-verses, these multi-verses are parallel to each others depending on the dimension.

Evidences for the origin of the universe that proven the bang of the energy is the cosmic microwave background radiation, the

Fig. 1. The Big Bang model alone cannot account for the uniform temperature of the CMB. A period of inflation is also necessary so that regions of the early Universe are close enough to thermally equalise. Credit: NASA/COBE

redshift of the spectrum which meant that the universe is expanding with high acceleration and abundance of different elements.

In the hypothesis of the virtual reality world I suppose that the nothing is just a bubble and the big bang inflated into this bubble making multi-verse in it, which are parallel to each others with ten dimensions, the first universe is the universe we are living in which is a 3D universe or 3D world and the 2D and 1D world live in the same universe of us, and there are universes of 4D,5D and etc till the 10D. The energy from the big bang led to formation of multi-verses by the action of budding universe.(3)

Each dimension for example the 4D can control over the descending dimension by some extra options offered for this yard and 5D is the same can control over the descending dimensions, but remember that all these are the information data that were scripted into the server of the highest civilization and this is just the result of the coded script, imagine it as the latex code we write for example S plus C equal etc and we get the result of what we need to build in the other side.(10)

The shape of the universe, there are three possibilities, the first one that we live in an open universe, the universe possess infinite number of stars and galaxies. The second possibility that we live in a closed universe, it's like there is a path without an end or a beginning, and it was supposed that if we travel along the extended path of the universe without any turn, we would return for our point of beginning again, but this proven wrong after the discovery of the expanding universe, the observer can observe that the entire universe is expanding very fast even faster than the speed of light, so according to theory of relativity, nothing can travel faster than the speed of light, but the universe is expanding faster than the speed of light, so imagine that you are travel beyond the entire universe and you started from any point at the extended path, you will never get back again to this point even if the universe is closed, because the universe is expanding faster than you, and you won't be able to discover beyond the universe or knowing it's end point because the universe is expanding faster than the speed of light, and also the farther the galaxies from each other, the more and more it will expand faster than the speed of light, but also the farther the two galaxies from each other the faster the distance will increases between them as if you have four galaxies at the same line the number one galaxy and number four galaxy will expand away from each others faster than number two and number three, the shape of the universe depending on it's density, so if the universe has a high density so we live in a closed universe and its shape is analogous to sphere, but if the universe has a low density so we live in an open universe and its shape analogous to saddle, but there is a third possibility, if the density is in between the closed universe

Fig. 2. Hyperspace

and the open universe so we live in flat universe, we almost observe the universe as a flat universe, because we can only observe the entire universe, not all the expanding universe, so we observe only small portion of it, so there is a difference of the shape of the observable universe and the whole universe.(4)

I suppose that the creator scripted that the universe is closed, so it's spherical in shape, so we are able to travel only by the surface and never go inside, because the density of the universe is high, the sphere of our universe is expanding and the rate of expanding is accelerating, and everything in the universe is moving in a straight line due to the force of the curved space time which generate force called gravity, moving in a strait lines if we observe the entire universe as we see it flat, but we see that everything is circling the space time curvature if we observe the whole universe, which means that the space time curved itself to form the closed universe, the expansion of the whole universe not increase the distances between the sun and other stars in the galaxy or the planet and it's moon, because these objects are forced by gravity, the only distances that increase are the distances between galaxies, if we draw a triangle in the sphere of our closed universe we will violate Euclidian geometry and it's angel will add up to greater than 180 degree.(16)

The design I supposed of parallel universes depend on the curvature of space time as well, as there is a parallel universe that exist in our region of the bubble universe, as we mentioned that there are multi-verses float like bubbles in a cosmic see of one large bubble, one of there parallel universes is in or curvature of closed universe but far away from us with Google years, no light can reach us from this universe because the universe is expanding faster than the speed of light, so we may never meet because imagine that our curved expanding accelerating universe having two sides, if we live in one side, the other universe exist parallel to us on the other side and according to philosophical concepts, this universe may got copy of our universe, but things can be slightly different, maybe it act like a mirror. (5)

The hypothesis of multi-verse, worlds that we can not see are supposed to be seven, one we live in, and the other is parallel to us at the same sphere, but in the opposite side.

The third universe is not like us, as it differs in dimensions, we are creatures live on the surface of the spherical closed 3D universe, but the third universe is a 4D universe which has 4

dimensions (Y,X,Z,T), imagine it on a scale, in the 4D you can control time, if you want to grow bigger or old and also the 4D can see the 3D creature, but if the 4D has creatures, the 3D can't see them. (13)

The 4th universe is a 5D universe where you can travel to any possible parallel universe that has the same initial coordinates and according to M-theory the hyperspace is formed from three spatial dimensions and one time dimension and 6 spatial small dimensions.

The 5th universe is a 6D universe where you can travel in time to any parallel universes that have the same coordinates. In the 6th universe, it's a 7D universe where you can travel to any world, no matter what are their coordinates. In the 7th universe, it's 8D universe where you can travel to any world without giving attention to their coordinates in time. In the 8th universe, it's 9D universe where you can record the history of all universes using it's initial coordinates. The 10 dimension is not imaginable where you cannot go beyond it's mortals

The energy that inflated into space began like Bang. The bang inflated to shape our 3D universe specially and related to this inflation and the condensed energy, there were high temperature and high pressure, so energy manifested itself into particles, tiny particles like gluons forming pairs of quarks which will destroy to give more gluons, we can say it's a kind of reproduction in particles, matter is all what existed in this event so now we have no anti-matter, by time the universe was stretched which led to colder space, so it will allow particles to interact giving atoms. so there is no more destruction of quarks to give back energy again, quarks formed new particles which are hadrons(protons and neutrons), then the neutrons decayed into protons to form the hydrogen atom, then the hydrogen gas clumped together with high temperature and pressure, nebulae are formed, but there must be some laws that control this, how can temperature and pressure act on the hydrogen atom, and how they interact with each others, so this is done by the natural laws, the natural laws are scripted into the server to help things come in relation to each other, to help the program run without any error, I can say it directly there is no interact from the higher civilization while the program is running, no interact till the end of the program, everything is coded, this programing languages is so accurate, that there is no fault. (12)

After the formation of nebulae they will be the factory to produce the first galaxies and stars, the nebulae are an interstellar cloud of dust and gas shaped in particulars shapes, so we can say the nebulae are the stars forming region, because it's so dense and hot environment for the dust and cloud of gas which will attract more energy, more hydrogen atoms more and more materials to make it hotter and when it become hot it will turn into a star, and if there is tiny amount of gas and dust left over, it may become planets, gas planets, and nebula may also form not just from gases of birth stars, but also from the death of stars, so there are nebulae we can see now by Hubble telescope like the orion nebulae and the planetary nebulae and etc..

The nebulae gave rise to many stars and each collection of stars called galaxy, galaxies like Milky way and Andromeda and etc so we now have a system of information that have been coded, but there is an important information to be coded to make it a perfect system, what if the energy ran off, how could the program continue, actually I imagine that before the creator submit the data, he checked an error line that told him that the energy will run off, so we must make the energy countless, but how, by something called supernova, so what is the scripted lines that the creator wrote in order this term of supernova gives him the perfect result, he scripted that when the stars core reaches the imbal-

ance which means that the radiation is not equal to the gravity, and this radiation is the form of energy produced by the fusion of the hydrogen into helium, the imbalance happen when there is no fusion in the core, as we mentioned the hydrogen fuse to helium in order to produce energy in the form of radiation the pushes against gravity, so there is balance between them and the star remain stable, when the hydrogen ran off, so the star fuse heavier element until they reach iron, but fusion of iron doesn't create or produce any kind of energy so the core of the star is builds up from iron until it reaches the critical amount and the imbalance between energy and gravity happen, so the core of the star collapses and the star implodes and the star feeds more mass and elements into the core and in this step all the heavier elements than iron is being created while the star dies in a supernova, the supernova is an explosion that create a neutron star if the star was not massive and if the star was massive enough it will create a black hole, the creation of rather neutron star or black hole comes from the collapse of the star core, and there are supernova remnants left over that will create nebulae from it's dust and clouds of gas under the effect of gravity and temperature, this nebulae will create other stars, small or moderate stars like our sun which will created due to the collapses of hydrogen and the clouds of gas under the effect of gravity, temperature and pressure, and also can create planets, comets and asteroids.

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Fig. 3. These nebulae seen by NASA's Spitzer Space Telescope, at left, may resemble two versions of the starship Enterprise from "Star Trek," overlaid at right. Credits: NASA/JPL-Caltech

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(1)

3.1.2. The origin of creatures and civilization

We are made of dust and gas, this is not just a sentence, but it's our truth, since the supernovae got place, the dust and gas were everywhere in space, every space got supernovae, so they share dust and gas, and this allowed our solar system to form and grow, and it's not just our solar system that had been formed those times, but many of stars system all over the space, and also the other 6 bubbles we imagine it in our whole bubble of our data. (11)

It was the chaotic birth, and it's like that everything must have a beginning, like the planets, it was once a seed, and it was hard to imagine how our Earth was like in it's early age, as it was like a fresh ball of molten lava, orbiting the sun and suffering the slams of meteors.

The creator's mind planned to make the use from the supernovae, as we said everything is related to each others, the event

of the supernova isn't just for the end of the stars ages, but for making the heavy planets and spread the heavy elements over the universe, and after the The Primordial Era, which was the Era of the beginning that included the big bang, inflation and natural laws till the formation of nebulae, and then came The Stelliferous Era on which the nebulae formed proto-stars and then we got galaxies.

The formation and evolution of the Solar System is estimated to have begun 4.568 billion years ago with the gravitational collapse of a small part of a giant molecular cloud. Most of the collapsing mass collected in the center, forming the Sun, while the rest flattened into a Proto-planetary disk out of which the planets, moons, asteroids, and other small Solar System bodies formed.

Before the evolution of the solar system, the Supernova exploded causing a gravito-thermal collapse in the Sun Nebula, then The planetesimal system formed, soon giving rise to protoplanets in the inner solar system, out to and including the current asteroid belt distance from Sun, the jovians Jupiter, Saturn, Neptune and Uranus, and the outer solar system icy planets.

In this era there were some 10-20 heavy eruptions from Sun in its T Tauri stage, rising temperatures by 700 Kelvin which called Hyperitanian period then the inner solar system was characterized by proto-planet collisions and terrestrial planet formation: Mercury, Venus, Proto-gaia (proto-earth), Theia and Mars which might be after Sun's T Tauri eruptions - this would then be one possible starting point of Hadean; most certainly Proto-gaia evolved some atmosphere soon after its creation. (Early Titanomachean) For a time after formation Proto-gaia was moonless, until Theia had grown to the size of current Mars. It is believed Theia was in Lagrange 4 coorbit (preceeding Trojan = same orbit but 30 angel degree forth) with Protogaia, but that position became unstable as Theia grew. Then Theia collided with Proto-gaia, and the major part became Earth, while some debris came in orbit around earth and assembled to Moon in some 10 years. It's very unclear whether this collision removed the atmosphere or not, some simulation numbers indicate a 50:50 probability whether removed or not removed. In either case the impact created a silicate atmosphere that is supposed to have cooled very fast. (6)

After the Earth swallowed the hypothetical planetoid Theia, the Moon formed all of the resulting debris which was not reabsorbed by the Earth. (2)

When the Earth is formed, we could talk about the Geological time scale, there are 4 Eons, HADEAN, ARCHEOZOIC, PROTEROZOIC which are precambrian eons and PHANEROZOIC.

The Hadean, the name of this eon came after hades the God of the under world because this eon was like a fresh molten lava ball orbiting the sun and trying to survive the slams of meteors, all these happened after the formation of the sun from cloud of dust and gas, then the middle of this cloud condensed to form the sun, the rest of the cloud flattened into a disc and separated into rings, overtime these particles gravitational fields affected one another until they formed the sun, the remnants of the formation of this gigantic ball of hot gas were hot, but they cooled down with time forming the planets as we mentioned before, but when the hadean eon began it's all about the formation of the Earth and drove it to the peaceful area, the formation of Earth like planet made under a process called planetary accretion, during that time the planet Thia hit the earth led to formation of larger Earth than before and some debris from the collision, the debris stuck close to Earth's orbit, then this debris formed the Earth's moon, the Earth was under the effect of pressure, temperature and mete-

ors that led it to form molten core that include heavier elements that sank into it, the dynamic effect on Earth led it to heat up to form 4 layer inner core, outer core, the mantle and crust, after the Earth has cooled down, water began to appear by the action of two models, inside-out model when the Earth's water formed by trace amount of water bonded to the minerals in the mantle and these water has been released through the out gassing of volcanoes on the surface, and the other model called the outside-in model which the water came from freezing meteorites and comets which collided with it's surface, then came the origin of the atmosphere, the primordial atmosphere was composed of hydrogen and helium, but this atmosphere lost due to the solar winds as the Earth magnetic field was not that hard enough to shield us from this. the collision that formed the moon had a very important role in forming the original atmosphere and also the gases from the magma, this original atmosphere was composed of methane, carbon dioxide, nitrogen, ammonia and water vapor.

The Archean, the first signs of tectonic plates appear at this era and also the first signs of life. molten lava from volcanic eruption cooled down to form volcanic islands, the meteors that brought water on Earth's surface contained carbon, proteins and amino acids.

In the deep ocean, it was a suitable environment for something to rise, by the combination and reaction of water seed with minerals and gases, microscopic Micro-organisms were formed, these micro organisms turned light into foods, according to mutations those bacteria differentiate from the original bacteria as Cyanobacteria then produced oxygen, oxygen filled in the ocean, the evidence for that is the deep sea iron rich rocks and Carbon compressed, but still no life in this era due to ultraviolet rays and the atmosphere is composed of 75 percent nitrogen and 15 percent carbon dioxide.

The presence of chemical soup began to form the start point in the way for a more complex life, the formation of MO that went through evolution through many Geological Eras, the first single celled Mo formed at the precambrian period, but it led to the cone of cambrian explosion, drove life to the complex life we live in now. (7)

3.1.3. The origin of curse and diseases

As the life started on Earth, the micro organisms began to spread all over the Earth, till this moment, our breathing air contains many bacteria, and our environment contains many inactive viruses, fungi and parasites, you might asked yourself what is the role of those organisms, just to achieve the life-cycle? - No, those MO have a role in the Equalism in this simulation, as they cause some of punishments or curse to other organisms, but how?

Any disease caused by MO, psychological disturbances and genetically.

By MO through bacteria, virus, fungi or parasite. Psychologically depending on emotions and the personality and genetically depending on the environment and mutations.

Diseases by MO maybe Inflammation, necrosis, gangrene, degeneration, congestion, embolism, thrombus, hemorrhage, infarction, ischaemia, tuberculosis, tumor. Any of these diseases have their mechanism, causes and types.

So the originate of MO is the key role of our disease, and disease is an important punishment used by the higher civilization to make the equalism. The role of emotions which come from the action of hormones is the key role of curse. (9)

3.1.4. The end scenario for the universe/multi-verse

We can make it clear about the end of the universe because we don't know what the dark matter is all about, since the universe is not all made of atoms, but dark matter and dark energy, so we don't know what is the fate of all these, but perhaps the creator scripted that the universe will end as the expanding energy will reach the absolute zero, and the universe will run out of energy, so the stars will run out of fuel and turn into black holes, so the black holes will conquer the universe, and the universe will become cold and lifeless, but the black holes will disappear by emitting hawking radiation. (15)

Summary

The hypothesis of the virtual reality world states that we are a lower civilization ruled and controlled by higher civilization that can control cosmic distances and threats by programming scripted data into action by special kind of programming languages, the programming took four sections which are **the origin of the universe** which is the stage where the universe began and sprung like inflated information and energy and formed from seven parallel universes or multi-verses arranged according to dimensions from 3D to 10D with differences with the abilities offered in each dimension by imagining that there is a place out of the cosmic space or cosmic bulk which is 11D at this dimension, the higher civilization exist and they can rule and control the cosmic bulk, this bulk consists of seven surfaces the first surface from the outside the bulk is the 10D, the 2d surface is the nine dimension, the third surface is the eight dimension, the fourth surface is the seven dimension, the fifth surface is the sixth dimension, the sixth surface is the fifth dimension and the seventh surface is the fourth dimension and the core surface is three dimension contains the one and two dimensions within.

Declaration

I declare that this thesis is an original report of my research, has been written by me and has not been submitted for any degree. The experimental work is almost entirely my own work, the collaborative contributions have been indicated clearly and acknowledged. Due references have been provided on all supporting literatures and resources.

Research statement

I am an astrophysics Researcher and Theorist with an interest in contributing to a deeper understanding of the Creator mind and the shape of our world including all the universes within. Human behavior is often characterized by deviations from perfect rationality and influenced by numerous factors that cloud the researcher's view of underlying causalities, human and demons are related by the game of life and I will work all my life to find the truth about the life we live in. I employ field, thinking and experiments, develop survey tools and analyze large panel data sets to better understand the life surrounding us and its psychological underpinnings, generating insights to inform theory as well as real world makers in the areas. The majority of my current research applies presumptions about the origin of the universe, the God mind and the design of innovation contests.

List of Figures

- 1 The Big Bang model alone cannot account for the uniform temperature of the CMB. A period of inflation is also necessary so that regions of the early Universe are close enough to thermally equalise. Credit: NASA/COBE 2
- 2 Hyperspace 3
- 3 These nebulae seen by NASA's Spitzer Space Telescope, at left, may resemble two versions of the starship Enterprise from "Star Trek," overlaid at right. Credits: NASA/JPL-Caltech 4

References

- [1] Bernd Aschenbach. Galactic supernova remnants. *Space Science Reviews*, 40(3-4):447–465, 1985.
- [2] Robin M Canup and Erik Asphaug. Origin of the moon in a giant impact near the end of the earth's formation. *Nature*, 412(6848):708–712, 2001.
- [3] Bernard Carr. *Universe or multiverse?* Cambridge University Press, 2007.
- [4] George FR Ellis. Cosmology: The shape of the universe. *Nature*, 425(6958):566–567, 2003.
- [5] Paul Halpern. The great beyond: higher dimensions, parallel universes and the extraordinary search for a theory of everything. *The Great Beyond: Higher Dimensions, Parallel Universes and the Extraordinary Search for a Theory of Everything*, by Paul Halpern, pp. 320. ISBN 0-471-74149-3. Wiley-VCH, August 2005., page 320, 2005.
- [6] Ch Hayashi, K Nakazawa, and Y Nakagawa. Formation of the solar system. In *Protostars and planets II*, pages 1100–1153, 1985.
- [7] James F Kasting. Methane and climate during the precambrian era. *Precambrian Research*, 137(3):119–129, 2005.
- [8] Eiichiro Kokubo and Shigeru Ida. Formation of protoplanets from planetesimals in the solar nebula. *Icarus*, 143(1):15–27, 2000.
- [9] Guido Majno and Isabelle Joris. *Cells, tissues, and disease: principles of general pathology*. Oxford University Press, 2004.
- [10] Zygmunt Morawski. Number of dimensions of the universe. *this website*.
- [11] Saul Perlmutter, G Aldering, M Della Valle, S Deustua, RS Ellis, S Fabbro, A Fruchter, G Goldhaber, DE Groom, IM Hook, et al. Discovery of a supernova explosion at half the age of the universe. *Nature*, 391(6662):51–54, 1998.
- [12] Maxim Pospelov. Particle physics catalysis of thermal big bang nucleosynthesis. *Physical review letters*, 98(23):231301, 2007.
- [13] Dennis Roseman. Reidemeister-type moves for surfaces in four-dimensional space. *Banach Center Publications*, 42:347–380, 1998.
- [14] Max Tegmark. Parallel universes. *Science and ultimate reality*, pages 459–491, 2004.
- [15] Artyom V Yurov, Artyom V Astashenok, and Pedro F Gonzalez-Diaz. Astronomical bounds on a future big freeze singularity. *Gravitation and Cosmology*, 14(3):205–212, 2008.
- [16] Ya Zel'dovich. Birth of a closed universe, and the anthropogenic principle. *Sov. Astron. Lett.(Engl. Transl.);(United States)*, 7(5), 1981.